

ENSURING THE ECONOMIC SECURITY OF AN ENTERPRISE IN MODERN CONDITIONS

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ABSTRACT

As a result of the economic reforms being carried out today, the activities of enterprises are carried out in the midst of various vagaries and opportunities arising from rapidly changing economic conditions. In the context of deepening global economic relations, intensifying competition and financial instability, the issue of economic security is gaining priority in enterprise management. Ensuring economic security is an important condition not only for the stable coverage of the current activities of the enterprise, but also for the implementation of its long-term development strategy.

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Economic security is a state of the economy in which its sustainable growth, adequate satisfaction of social needs, high quality of management, and protection of economic interests at the national and international levels are ensured. [1]

The economic security of an enterprise is also achieved through the effective management of its internal resources, ensuring financial stability, adapting to market conditions and making strategic decisions. This concept is not simply about improving financial results, but rather the process of making an enterprise capable of achieving these results — namely, sustainable growth, through early identification of risks, monitoring, assessment, and consistent management mechanisms (Shynkar, Gontar & Dubyna, 2020).

Traditional management methods cannot fully cover the complex nature of modern economic threats. Therefore, there is a need to introduce new mechanisms based on innovative approaches to ensuring economic security.

The economic security of an enterprise represents the degree of protection of its financial condition, production potential, investment opportunities, and intellectual resources from internal and external negative factors. A low level of economic security can lead to a deterioration in the stability of the enterprise, financial losses, and a decrease in

competitiveness. Therefore, the issue of economic security should be considered as an integral component of the enterprise's strategic management system.

These threats require new approaches to ensuring the economic security of an enterprise.

In modern conditions, one of the important factors in preventing economic risks is the widespread use of digital technologies. Analytical information systems, based on big data and artificial intelligence, allow for early detection of possible threats through systematic monitoring of economic processes and their elimination.

In addition, a wide opportunity has been created to increase the effectiveness of ensuring economic security by organizing an integrated risk management system. This system serves to comprehensively assess financial, operational and strategic risks in the activities of an enterprise and simultaneously reduce the risks that have arisen.

Ensuring information security is also one of the important innovative areas of economic security, preventing economic losses by reducing cyber risks and protecting intellectual property.

An integrated approach is necessary to ensuring the economic security of an enterprise. The economic security of the enterprise is strengthened by rational use of strengths and opportunities, gradual elimination of weaknesses, and preliminary assessment of external threats. Below are the aspects that should be paid attention to when ensuring the stability of the enterprise, developed using SWOT analysis.

The results of the SWOT analysis create an important scientific basis for making strategic decisions to ensure the economic security of the enterprise and strengthen its financial stability. The analysis allows for a comprehensive assessment of strengths and weaknesses, as well as opportunities and threats arising from the external environment.

In short, in modern market conditions, traditional management methods cannot fully ensure the economic security of the enterprise. Therefore, innovative approaches, including digital technologies, big data analysis, artificial intelligence, integrated risk management systems, and information security mechanisms, are effective tools for strengthening economic security.

Strategic conclusions developed on the basis of SWOT analysis allow for increasing financial stability by rational use of the strengths and existing opportunities of the enterprise, eliminating weaknesses, and minimizing external threats.

These approaches serve to strengthen the financial stability of the enterprise, reduce risks, and implement long-term strategic goals. The scientific analyses and recommendations presented in the thesis serve as a basis for improving the mechanisms for managing the economic security of the enterprise in practice..

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